

STRENGTHENING HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS' HUMAN CAPITAL TO NAVIGATE NEW CHALLENGES THROUGH MUTUAL LEARNING: LESSONS LEARNED FROM HORIZON EUROPE PROJECTS

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Abstract

The European Research Area (ERA) aims to reduce the fragmentation within the European Union's research and innovation system (R&I), requiring European Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to continuously adapt and transform to create a single market for research and innovation [1]. Moreover, to better respond to these goals, the Council of the EU adopted the first ERA Policy Agenda for 2022-2024 [2], which outlines specific actions that will have a significant impact on HEIs in several areas of R&I. These include research infrastructures, open science, transnational and international cooperation, gender balance, joint programming, researchers' careers' development, researchers' mobility, and structural reforms. In this evolving landscape, HEIs will need to foster closer cooperation to establish systems that promote synergies, dialogue and transferable skills through knowledge sharing and mutual learning (MML) practices [3].

The relevance of mutual learning as a methodology to strengthen the capacity of HEIs to advance towards the ERA priorities is proven by the experience of three EU-funded projects coordinated by the Projects Department of APRE, the Italian Agency for the Promotion of European Research (CATALISI, TIME4CS, PATTERN) [4].

Through mutual learning, TIME4CS aimed at supporting HEIs in implementing sustainable institutional changes to promote public engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology. This methodology is used by the CATALISI project, which enables HEIs to pursue institutional transformation, conceiving the mutual learning as an "acceleration service" for strengthening human capital, capacity building and outreach. Strengthening HEIs is also central in another Horizon Europe project: PATTERN promotes the practice of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) by developing and piloting training activities on transferable skills for researchers at all stages of their careers.

Based on the evidence from the implementation of these projects, this article highlights the need for HEIs to broaden their traditional collaborative approaches, suggesting that they embrace a culture of mutual learning through peer-to-peer interactions to harness knowledge exchange and foster skills development. This shift is crucial for HEIs to effectively address evolving challenges. It also advocates improving HEIs' configuration, their governance change and enhancing their capacity to manage R&I effectively over time.

Keywords: Knowledge sharing, mutual learning sharing, Knowledge management, Higher education institutions, ERA challenges.

1 INTRODUCTION

The idea of developing a European Research Area (ERA) to overcome the fragmentation of the European Union's Research and Innovation system divided between national and European interests was launched in 2000 in the framework of the Lisbon Strategy and was given a legal basis in 2009 with the entry into force of the Treaty of Lisbon. In fact, article 179 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) clearly states the need for the Union "of strengthening its scientific and technological bases by achieving a European Research Area in which researchers, scientific knowledge and technology circulate freely, and encouraging it to become more competitive, including in its industry" [1]. Since that time, the creation of a single market for research and innovation (R&I) in Europe and the promotion of a fruitful European research environment have become priorities of the EU policies and programmes.

The establishment of these priorities paved the way for a series of actions and initiatives (e.g. plans for European Research Infrastructures, the European Charter for Researchers, the Code of Conduct for

the Recruitment of Researchers, the EURAXESS initiative, the Open Science initiative, the European Open Science Cloud – EOSC [2]) which have led to major achievements over the last 20 years. Nevertheless, new societal, environmental, economic and geopolitical challenges affecting the EU in the last years require new strategies for the actors of the EU R&I policy. In this context, the role of the ERA is crucial, mainly because of its ability to bring together the national and the European levels of R&I policy and its pursuit of the principle of excellence.

In order to guarantee that the new ERA is able to address the global challenges, the European Commission has identified four strategic objectives [2] – i) prioritising investments and reforms, ii) improving access to excellence, iii) translating R&I results into the economy, iv) deepening the ERA – whose achievement constitutes the basis of the actions developed and included in the ERA Policy Agenda 2022-2024. In fact, considering the EU strategic documents¹ on this topic, the EU identifies 4 priority areas and 20 actions in which to invest aiming at enhancing the European single market for research and innovation. To this end, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) **have a key role to play and need to be empowered** “to develop in line with the ERA and in synergy with the European Education Area” [3]. Universities are crucial actors not only in driving progress towards research and scientific excellence but also in catalysing and disseminating knowledge, developing incubators of talents among graduates and researchers, bringing new technologies to the market, improving public services and addressing societal challenges.

In line with the ERA policy’s objectives, in particular, with the fourth objective (Deepening the ERA) and with Action 13 of the ERA Policy Agenda – Empower HEIs to develop in line with the ERA and in synergy with the European Education Area, APRE, the Agency for the Promotion of the European Research², is coordinating one H2020 funded project and two Horizon Europe funded projects worthy of interest in terms of empowering Higher Education Institutions. These projects are TIME4CS - Supporting sustainable Institutional Changes to promote Citizen Science in Science and Technology (G.A. 101006201), CATALISI – Catalysation of institutional transformations of HEIs through the adoption of acceleration services (G.A. 101094917) and PATTERN – Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings towards the Enhancement of Research Networks (G.A. 101094416). Although the three projects address diverse specific objectives, they all are implementing the knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology in key activities in support of HEIs.

Based on the experiences gained from the implementation of the three above-mentioned projects, the paper aims at providing reflections, good practices and insights related to the use of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning as a key method to support HEIs and Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) to adapt to the evolving R&I landscape and to advance towards the ERA policy’s objectives and priorities, which requires continuous efforts to better address HEIs’ pressing global challenges.

2 METHODOLOGY

In the globalized and interconnected world, cross-border cooperation and common mechanisms have become essential for addressing pressing global challenges. In this context and within the R&I fields, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning approach can be considered a powerful tool through which HEIs can introduce changes in their organizations in an efficient way by earning mutual benefit [4]. Projects such as TIME4CS, CATALISI and PATTERN experienced how this approach is solid and can support HEIs in establishing a permanent and continuous cooperation across Europe and beyond. Nonetheless, it represents an important enabler for improving HEIs’ capacity to encourage the free circulation of students and researchers and promoting scientific knowledge and technology.

In the framework of these three projects, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning is a learning method as well as a strategic approach to institutional changes [5]. On the one hand, it can be considered a **learning method** since it implies a constant exchange of information, experiences, competences, and know-how between learners through which they broaden their knowledge and skills.

¹ They are: the EC Communication “A new ERA for Research and Innovation” (September 2020), the Council conclusions on the “New European Research Area” (December 2020), the Council conclusions on “Deepening the ERA: providing researchers with attractive and sustainable careers and working conditions and making brain circulation a reality” (May 2021), the “Global approach to Research and Innovation (September 2021).

² APRE, the Agency for the Promotion of the European Research, is an Italian non-profit association created in 1989 as a joint initiative of the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research and a number of public and private bodies, to meet the growing demand for information on European Research and Innovation (R&I) programmes. Nowadays, APRE is at the heart of a network of more than 150 members from the academia to private sector. Its mission is to support and promote Italian participation in EU (R&I) programmes, by providing scientific and industrial communities with information, training and assistance services.

In this perspective, the approach fosters a greater collective capacity of problem solving in specific areas of interest and promotes a culture of change. On the other hand, mutual learning is a valuable strategic approach to introduce permanent **changes in an institution**. In this regard, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning can be a powerful catalyst for permanent institutional transformation, influencing not only regulatory frameworks but also social and behavioural norms within HEIs and Research Performing Organizations (RPOs). By mobilizing relevant stakeholders, it becomes a new way for HEIs to pursue sustainable change and addressing complex challenges of our time.

TIME4CS³ is a H2020 funded project that aimed at facilitating a way in which the scientific ecosystem could better take societal views into consideration by supporting RPOs - i.e. research entities such as universities and research centres - in defining and implementing institutional changes that can lead to a better and more effective engagement of citizens in research and innovation. Through the development and the adoption of a knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan, the project, ended in December 2023, successfully supported the RPOs partners of the Consortium in the implementation of actions leading to Institutional Changes to promote Public Engagement (citizens and citizens associations) and Citizen Science (CS) in science and technology.

CATALISI⁴ is an ongoing project funded by Horizon Europe that aims at supporting HEIs to implement a strategy and individual pathway for institutional transformation through the adoption of targeted and innovative *acceleration services*. Among the seven acceleration services that the project is developing and testing, the one named under “Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach” is based on the use of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology to strengthen human capital and create a collaborative knowledge-based environment. In this case too, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning plan developed within the project has the double aim of fostering the circulation of knowledge, experiences and good practices to allow HEIs to find workable solutions to advance in the transformation in the intervention areas of their interest and of being a valuable approach to facilitate the social patterns’ change within the HEIs.

PATTERN⁵ is an ongoing Horizon Europe funded project whose main goal is to promote the practice of Open and Responsible Research and Innovation by developing and piloting training activities for researchers at all stages of their careers. The trainings focusing on transferable skills aim at empowering HEIs and RPOs to embrace a transformative process to improve the excellence of the science conducted, the capacity within the ERA to tackle societal challenges and the interaction between science and society. Although to a small extent compared to TIME4CS and CATALISI, this project relies on mutual learning when it comes to co-design the training cycles and the policy recommendations through a participatory approach that considers and involves relevant stakeholders and end-users.

The following paragraphs present the main results achieved by the projects so far and will show the potential of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning as a powerful tool for HEIs and RPOs to broaden their cooperative approaches, to address global and societal challenges and to improve their governance mechanisms to be able to manage R&I effectively over time and to actively advance towards the deepening of the ERA.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Good practices on the knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology from the TIME4CS project

The main goal of TIME4CS project is to support and facilitate the implementation of sustainable Institutional Changes in Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) to promote Public Engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology. To achieve its overall aim, TIME4CS has identified 4 Intervention Areas (IAs) that alone or combined can stimulate the Institutional Changes necessary to promote Citizen Science in Research and Innovation processes: 1) Research, 2) Education and Awareness, 3) Support resources and Infrastructure and 4) Policy and Assessment. TIME4CS analyses these areas to consolidate the knowledge about the institutional adoption, establishment and maintenance of Citizen Science capacity and to establish a model for Citizen Science expansion through Institutional Changes.

³ <https://www.time4cs.eu/>

⁴ <https://catalisi.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.pattern-openresearch.eu/>

For each Intervention Area, TIME4CS has identified an organization that has already undergone some institutional changes to promote Citizen Science showing therefore a comprehensive knowledge and expertise on the matter. The knowledge of these partners, called Front-Runners (FRs), contributes to the definition of a set of practical actions aimed at paving the way to Institutional Changes, defined as Grounding Actions (GAs). FRs interacted with and mentored four organizations willing to face the challenge of introducing Citizen Science more and more in their structures. These organizations, defined as Implementers (Is), within TIME4CS lifetime developed tailored roadmaps including a specific set of Grounding Actions to carry out, benefitting from the constant support of Front-Runners. The interaction between Front-Runners and Implementers took place during the whole TIME4CS lifetime through the development of a Mutual Learning and Knowledge exchange framework designed to support the implementation and the evaluation of the Grounding Actions leading to Institutional Changes, with the ultimate goal of encouraging public engagement and Citizen Science in science and technology.

3.1.1 The key role played by the knowledge sharing and mutual learning Programme

In the TIME4SC project, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning was considered a learning method paramount for the achievement of the overall objective of the project, namely, to support the institutional adoption of Citizen Science by triggering the development of sustainable Institutional Changes in the governance and in the structural organization of RPOs.

The developed programme was aimed at facilitating the exchange of experiences and the co-creation of common solutions to similar problems, and at capitalizing on shared experiences and the set of best practices and lesson learnt collected throughout the project's activities. Namely, it was established between the more experienced and the less experienced project's partners built upon the exchange of experiences and points of view between the different organizations, and, as such, it was primarily aimed at concretely supporting the Is in the definition and carrying out of selected Grounding Actions (GAs), as detailed in their tailored roadmaps towards institutional change, benefitting from the expertise of the more experienced partners. At the same time, the exchange proved to be beneficial for the FRs themselves, that thanks to their mentoring role had the opportunity to learn more about needs and challenges in different environments and to gain insights into the replicability of specific actions in different contexts.

With those overall objectives established, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme provided partners with practical knowledge and concrete examples and inputs for the implementation of the GAs, to capitalize on the experience of the more experienced organisations and to create a common framework for the process of developing and implementing institutional roadmaps, contributing to increase knowledge on how to stimulate institutional changes thanks to the experience in TIME4CS.

3.1.2 The knowledge sharing and mutual learning events

Three main types of knowledge sharing and mutual learning events were planned: i) Knowledge sharing from Front-Runners to Implementers, ii) Mentoring Visits, iii) Co-creation and co-designing events.

3.1.2.1 Knowledge sharing from Front-Runners to Implementers

This type of event was aimed at gathering knowledge from the Front-Runners for the definition of concrete Grounding Actions in each intervention area defining best practices and lessons learnt as basis for the development of the roadmaps towards institutional change and at supporting Implementers in the design phase of their individual roadmaps with Front-Runners sharing their know-how and success and/or failure factors. Four online workshops (one for each intervention area) have been organised with the support of digital collaborative tools (i.e. Miro) to make the format more interactive and foster more active participation: i) Education & Awareness, ii) Research, iii) Support Resources and Infrastructure, iv) Policy and assessment.

Figure 1 – Knowledge sharing and mutual learning Programme in TIME4CS

The activity proved to be very helpful for Implementers in the further definition of the GAs and in the development of the first version of their roadmaps.

3.1.2.2 Mentoring Visits

Four onsite mentoring visits were organised, one by each Implementer, hosting the Front-Runners and the stakeholders (core team) involved in the implementation phase. The visits mainly aimed at discussing the progress and needs of the Implementers, benefitting from suggestions from Front-Runners and from their direct interaction with the local environment.

The mentoring programme was complemented by a series of regular online exchanges between Front-Runners and Implementers to discuss the details of the implementation of the Grounding Actions. The series consisted of quarterly meetings alternating two different formats designed to facilitate the follow-up of activities, achievements and challenges of each Implementer while also sharing experiences with other Implementers or with the Front Runners. The two formats of the online exchanges were:

- Implementers Forum – attended by representatives of all Implementer RPOs, who presented and discussed among them their progresses, challenges and opportunities for each specific GA in their roadmap, answering a pre-defined set of detailed explorative questions. The Forum was carried out with the support of APRE and other facilitators who helped the discussion.
- Implementers Journeys – these virtual meetings, one per Implementer, were attended by representatives of the specific RPO, Front-Runners, supporting partners, and other stakeholders. Based on a reporting template, each Implementer shared the process of working with the selected GAs, and got dedicated time by Front-Runners, including tailored feedback and support.

3.1.2.3 Co-creation and co-designing events

This activity, part of the knowledge sharing and mutual learning programme, was mainly aimed at co-producing with local stakeholders of each Higher Education Institution the roadmaps for the realisation of each Grounding Action. Each event had different objectives and expected outcomes. In particular:

- The first co-creation event aimed at co-designing the first version of the roadmaps and the definition of Grounding Actions to include in close collaboration with the local actors that would be involved in the different actions.
- The second co-creation event aimed at discussing and evaluating the implementation of the Grounding Actions, after one year of activities, with local actors. Based on this discussion, possible adjustments to the roadmaps were proposed.
- The third co-creation event aimed to discuss the achievements, the impacts, and the sustainability of the implemented Grounding Actions and to discuss the medium- to long-term evolution of the goals of each roadmap on sustainable Institutional Changes for the

implementing organizations with the support of the ecosystem of actors built during the project implementation.

3.1.3 Reflections on the added value provided by the knowledge sharing and mutual learning approach in TIME4CS

Considering the overall TIME4CS objective, the knowledge sharing and mutual learning approach proved to be very effective. In fact, HEIs and RPOs had the opportunity to be at the core of a long transformation process leading to the promotion and then to the increasing implementation of Citizen Science as research methodology within their institutions.

The application of the mutual learning methodology for the implementation of an institutional change allowed each organisation with different needs and institutional frameworks to benefit from the exchange and mentoring support of Front-Runners. This implied the exchange among universities focusing on common challenges faced in the implementation of their Grounding Actions and discussing possible solutions to overcome them, based on the common experience they were going through as part of the TIME4CS project. All this with a continuous attention on the local specificities of each organisation. Furthermore, the FRs had the chance to reflect on their own citizen science-related practices, gathering useful insights to renew or improve their already well-established organisational context and role in the field. And finally, through participating in the mutual learning events, the Front-Runners also realized that each institution is different and thus, the path and Grounding Actions leading to the institutional changes needed to support Citizen Science, are dependent on each institutional context.

The TIME4CS experience represents a success story of how the knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology can serve the ERA policy objectives, especially the ERA Policy Agenda's Action 13. Indeed, it provided a new and better way for universities to work together across borders by acknowledging that they are at the centre of local innovation ecosystems and the added value of an intensive collaboration with non-academic organisations. Moreover, the project proved to be a good practice showing how HEIs and RPOs can "contribute effectively to the enhancement of learning in a societal environment characterised by high levels of uncertainty and complexity and are dedicated to creating public value via a process of open engagement, mutual learning, discovery and exchange with all stakeholders in society -local, national and international" [6].

3.2 Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach, through knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology in CATALISI project

The CATALISI project support HEIs to effectively implement strategies and tailor-made pathways for their institutional transformation through the adoption of *Acceleration Services*. One of the key Acceleration Services is Reinforce Human Capital: capacity building and outreach, by creating a collaborative knowledge-based environment that can facilitate peer networking to accelerate progress in key areas outlined in the European Research Area (ERA) agenda (such as strengthening research careers, gender equality plans and reform of career and research assessment, mainstreaming open science, institutional strategy development in research and innovation). By knowledge sharing and mutual learning activities, universities can address and overcome challenges more effectively, fostering a collaborative environment conducive to meaningful progress and sustainable change in the higher education landscape. The starting point in the process of encouraging and supporting mutual learning dynamics to integrate the endeavours of the HEIs in the development of institutional transformations in the field of R&I, is the organization of Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops and Twinning activities by each HEI participating in the Consortium.

The HEIs involved in CATALISI are in seven different European countries: Greece (Aristotle University of Thessaloniki), Lithuania (Kaunas University of Technology), Ireland (University College Cork), Poland (University of Gdańsk), Spain (Jaume I University), Italy (Luiss Guido Carli University), Netherlands (Amsterdam University Medical Centre).

They cover a wide range of disciplines and geographical locations and have different profile and operates in a unique local context with specific needs.

3.2.1 Mobilisation and Mutual Learning (MML) workshops

Although CATALISI is still a work in progress project, initial reflections can already be made on the knowledge and mutual learning approach adopted in terms of its contribution to the institutional transformation that the universities are undertaking.

Seven MML workshops will be organised by each of the participating universities, focusing on specific R&I topics of interest. So far, two MML workshops have already been organised, one at the Jaume I University (Spain) on 19 January 2024 and a second one at the Amsterdam University Medical Centre (Netherlands) on 11 April 2024. The following sections present the main general aspects of this methodology and what has already emerged from these two experiences.

Figure 2 – MML workshop in Jaume I University (Spain)

Figure 3 – MML workshop in Amsterdam University Medical Centre (Netherlands)

3.2.2 Basic features of CATALISI MML workshops

In the CATALISI project, MML workshops are built upon the exchange of experiences and points of view related to institutional transformation in specific R&I topics, bringing together participants with different levels of experience who have learned from their own experience and can share it to others which need support for their actions.

Each CATALISI MML workshop will provide participants with **practical knowledge, concrete examples and inputs to achieve and manage institutional change over time in the areas of intervention they deem necessary**. At the Jaume I University, the MML workshop was organised around the theme of 'Research Ethics and Integrity', while at the University Medical Centre Amsterdam, the focus was on 'Promoting Responsible Conduct of Research'. Despite the different themes, the MML workshops will serve:

- Deepen and transfer the knowledge with regards to the respective topic
- Identify good practices and common solutions already in place,
- explore new scenarios to improve, advance and consolidate the process of institutional transformation in the organization.

CATALISI considers knowledge exchange and mutual learning both as a learning method and as a general approach to institutional change, involving different levels of knowledge exchange. In CATALISI, knowledge exchange and mutual learning is therefore seen as a dynamic and evolving process, depending on the different phases of the project and the needs of the actors involved.

Therefore, the most important and preliminary step is to **define the topics of the MML workshop**. It is important that the universities organise the MML workshop based on their needs and priorities regarding the area of intervention in which they will carry out their institutional transformation. It is essential to optimise the content and agenda of the workshops by focusing on specific actions to be taken, for which collaboration with other universities can facilitate the process.

Moreover, APRE has defined **a structure** for the CATALISI MML workshop, which should normally include a first session dedicated to inspiring examples from the host university on the chosen theme, a second session dedicated to the co-creation of new ways for institutional change in this area, through the exchange of possible solutions, obstacles encountered, impact and sustainability of the actions implemented, and a final session with an evaluation exercise to collect direct feedback from the participants. This predefined structure also allows each university to acquire a replicable technique that can be applied each time a new MML workshop is organised on a different theme.

3.2.3 *Participants' commitment and roles*

In CATALISI, the collaborative and interactive nature of the MML workshops facilitates peer networking and mutual learning among participants.

Participants of the MML workshops are mainly from the universities involved in the consortium, which will benefit from each other's experience, but may also include external experts invited to the workshops (e.g. from other similar EU projects) as well as other stakeholders from the quadruple helix⁶. On the one hand, the exchange of knowledge and experience among the HEIs (peers) supports mutual learning about how other similar organizations have already implemented specific institutional changes. On the other hand, HEIs benefit from knowledge exchange with external experts and from the involvement of quadruple helix stakeholders. This multiplayer approach allows the knowledge sharing and mutual learning workshop to extend the actors involved in the areas of interest to other networks, alliances of universities and surrounding ecosystem actors, which is a key approach to contribute and deliver impactful outcomes (e.g. action plans, agreements, collaborations) in the areas of institutional change.

Specifically, the actors which are encouraged to participate are:

- Those from different hierarchical levels within the organization (low, middle and top managers): it is an important aspect is to include person(s) with sufficient seniority among the participants (including top level managers), as a person with experience and knowledge of the chosen theme will be able to commit the institution to institutional change.
- Those outside the organizing team: seeking collaboration between different groups (i.e. researchers, support staff, governance members, etc.) within each organization and departments within the university, is deemed necessary.
- External actors from the quadruple helix and experts for keynotes speeches (if needed).

In MML workshops organized by HEIs, it has been noticed that encouraging the active participation of such actors is key. This is achieved by promoting open dialogue and facilitating the exchange of diverse perspectives and insights, in order to maximise the results. By creating a supportive and inclusive environment, organizers and one or more facilitators need to well-design activities and discussions, empower participants to share their experiences, challenges and best practices, thus enriching the learning experience for all. Skilled facilitation also helps to ensure that workshop objectives are clearly communicated and that participants remain focused and motivated throughout the session. Most of the success of the mobilization and mutual learning workshops lies in a **culture of collaboration and mutual respect**; only in a dynamic space can knowledge sharing lead to innovation and collective solutions as outcomes.

3.3 **PATTERN: the role of mutual learning in the trainings' development**

The focus of PATTERN's project is different from the previous projects: it is not about institutional transformation but on the cultivation of inclusive and sustainable practices in Open Science (OS) and Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) through promoting researcher's training in the relevant transferable skills. The project, that is now in its core phase encompassing the development of the training modules on eight transferable skills (Open Access, FAIR data Management, Citizen Science, Research Integrity, Gender, non-discrimination and inclusion in research, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, Science Communication (towards media and policy makers), and Management and Leadership) and the first cycle of piloting activities, embeds the mutual learning approach as important component of its overall methodology.

⁶ The quadruple helix is the model that recognizes the interaction between academia, industry, government and civil society within a knowledge ecosystem.

Figure 4 – PATTERN methodology

The mutual learning is embedded in the co-creation and co-design phase which crosses all project's running phases. Such methodology has been used during the mapping and analysis of training activities, models of trainings and platforms on Open RRI carried out in the first year of the project. During this phase that led to more than 500 resources mapped, the organisation of mutual learning events served to identify existing and emerging practices in face-to-face, online and asynchronous learning.

3.3.1 The impact of mutual learning events in PATTERN

The three mutual learning events (MLEs) organized and facilitated by one of the project's partners aimed at identifying existing practices on open and responsible trainings, understanding current trends in different modes of learning and for different target groups, and reaching experts and participants on a global scale, including widening countries. These activities supported the mapping and analysis carried out, in addition to forming the basis for the quality assessment of trainings, together with the mapping. Each mutual learning event followed a specific methodology tailored to its respective goal and audience and built upon the previous one.

The first MLE focused on the identification of existing practices and on supplementing mapping activities by leveraging the expertise within the whole consortium. Thus, only PATTERN project partners took part in it.

The second MLE aimed to engage experts in a dialogue about ongoing activities and emerging trends in open science training. The goal was to explore both successful aspects and challenges while generating innovative training concepts. The MLE drew participation of both PATTERN project partners and external experts, covering five key topics: technological trends (online, face-to-face, asynchronous formats); pedagogical trends for early career researchers; pedagogical trends for late-career researchers; learning outcomes; and sustainability and impact. Eventually, participants covered success factors, challenges, needs, aspirations and requirements, and recommendations, providing a comprehensive exploration of the landscape of open science training [7].

The third MLE was intended to deliberate on the outcomes and recommendations from the second one, encompassing key trends and insights, and it was attended by global experts representing diverse countries. various topics were established, and participants chose a topic to discuss in groups before rotating to another topic for further discussion with different participants. Finally, rapporteurs presented the key findings for each topic to the entire audience [7].

The Mutual Learning Events provided valuable information on key trends in Open Science trainings useful to inform the next steps in PATTERN, proving, once again, to be relevant for better understanding and capturing success factors, challenges, and recommendations for the development of trainings foreseen by the project. Eventually, the MLEs representing an authentic enabler for the whole project's implementation, thus paving the way to a tailored and actual gaps-based path towards the successful design, piloting and consolidation of innovative training modules for researchers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The experience of the three European-funded projects coordinated by APRE underscores the significance of incorporating key features and attending to some pertinent details by universities to ensure the efficacy of knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodologies in addressing Research and Innovation (R&I) challenges and advancing European Research Area (ERA) policy objectives.

Central to the success of the use of knowledge sharing and mutual learning methodology in these projects can be summarized in the following provisions for:

1. Clear definition of the themes, the main area of interest of the universities.
2. Clear identification of objectives to guide the direction and focus of knowledge-sharing activities.
3. Wide involvement of heterogeneous stakeholders (inside and outside universities), particularly those pertinent to the chosen topic, to ensure diverse perspectives and expertise are considered.
4. Appointment of a skilled facilitator (even external to the university), which may help in the creation of templates and guidelines to streamline the organization process as well as in facilitating the engagement during events.
5. Use of co-creative tools to foster collaborative problem-solving and innovation.
6. Customization to accommodate specific needs and adapt to individual local and institutional contexts, thereby enhancing relevance and effectiveness.

The concept of mutual learning, exemplified by the collaborative experiences of three European-funded projects coordinated by APRE is a keystone for higher education institutions facing the challenges of European Research Area (ERA) policy implementation. Universities today find themselves in a dynamic landscape where collaboration and mutual learning are essential.

Beyond its immediate application in the context of specific initiatives, the mutual learning approach is emerging to contribute not only to the continuous improvement of individual knowledge bases, but also to the adaptation of the entire university organization, institutional norms, and procedures in the field of R&I.

TIME4CS and CATALISI projects underline the importance of institutional adaptability, demonstrating how institutions can evolve by learning from other experiences in the adoption of changes (new norms and protocols) laid down by the ERA policy. At the same time, initiatives such as PATTERN highlight the central role of knowledge and mutual learning in the co-creation and co-design of trainings for researchers, an activity that well addresses the Action 13 of the ERA Policy Agenda highlighting the need for a policy approach aiming at equipping researchers with those transferable skills useful for an interoperable career in academia and beyond [3].

By fostering a culture of continuous learning and skills development among faculty, staff and students, universities can cultivate the expertise needed to deal effectively with the complexities of modern higher education. A collective learning process among universities also requires a mindset of openness and collaboration among institutions, but also with other external stakeholders.

In an increasingly interconnected world, universities recognize the importance of working together and sharing knowledge with their counterparts, with a clear methodology.

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